

GLITSS POLICY BRIEF

Turning GLITSS Insights into Policy Impact

The Flow of Illicit Antiquities:

The Balkans as a Major Corridor for Cultural Heritage Smuggling

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Key Messages

- ✓ **A Multi-Million Euro Enterprise:** The illicit antiquities trade in the EU operates at significant scale, generating millions of euros annually for organised crime.
- ✓ **Balkan Smuggling Corridors:** Highly organised criminal networks systematically exploit Balkan routes between West Asia and the main EU markets — Austria, Germany and Switzerland.
- ✓ **Conflict-Zone Sourcing:** Artefacts enter the EU from conflict and crisis zones, including Iraq, Syria and Ukraine, via these Balkan routes.
- ✓ **Fragmented Governance:** National actions and processes are inharmonious, and regional cooperation among Balkan states remains weak.

Context & Purpose

According to research conducted for the [European Commission](#) on Illicit Trade in Cultural Objects in Europe (2019), more than 298,000 ancient or historic coins and 140,000–700,000 other antiquities — worth an estimated €120–374 million — are sold annually by European dealers. This brief examines the Balkans as a critical transit corridor for this trade and identifies the criminal, market and institutional weaknesses that allow it to flourish.

Over 2,000 artefacts originating from Ukraine seized in Serbia in 2020 (photo: Serbian Customs Administration)

Insights & Findings

Findings reported to GLITSS workshops and an associated COST STSM survey cluster across three dimensions of the trade:

1. Criminal Networks & Methods

- **Online social organisation of crime:** Looters and traffickers organise activities in public and private online forums, social networks and social media.
- **Organised gangs:** Many professional criminal teams plunder archaeological sites, smuggle antiquities, or fabricate paperwork to corroborate misdeclarations of origin, authenticity, legality and value; some are poly-criminal enterprises that also handle drugs and arms.
- **Fakes:** A significant number of “illicit antiquities” are in fact high-quality fakes manufactured to market to Western collectors.
- **Criminal violence:** There have been threats and acts of violence against archaeologists.

2. Conflict, Markets & Political Risk

- **Polluted EU market:** Looted antiquities and fakes alike are sold through dealers and auction houses, or directly to collectors, in north-western Europe.
- **Difficult-to-police markets:** Some stolen cultural goods are trafficked onward to Russia.
- **Political instability and the rule of law:** Looters, traffickers, collectors and protectors of looters and traffickers have included national, military and international police officers, peacekeepers, and violent political extremists; smugglers have included forced migrants who are subsistence criminals, and professional criminals hiding among asylum-seekers.
- **Cultural and religious desecration:** Significant underwater, underground and standing archaeological, historic and religious sites — including churches, mosques and graves — are seriously damaged.

3. Enforcement & Governance Gaps

- **Under-staffing at borders:** Customs and other border authorities lack the staff or time for extensive searches of the huge volumes of goods passing through borders, airports and seaports — e.g. Koper port checks only 2% of containers.
- **Under-training and under-resourcing:** Most state officials lack adequate knowledge to recognise protected cultural goods, a problem worsened by a dearth of professional equipment.
- **No common rulebook:** There is no universal manual for authorities on cultural heritage; some countries have basic guides, others have

none, and coordination between Balkan countries is scarce and limited.

Policy Relevance

This policy brief aligns with several EU strategic frameworks:

- [EU Security Union Strategy 2020–2025](#)
- [EU Strategy to Tackle Organised Crime 2021–2025](#)
- [EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026](#)
- [Council of the European Union’s Conclusions on the Fight against Trafficking in Cultural Goods](#)
- [Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025–2027](#)
- [EU Action Plan against Trafficking in Cultural Goods](#)

Recommendations

- ✓ **Strengthen Intelligence-Sharing & Law Enforcement:** Build national and regional intelligence-gathering and enforcement capacity through multinational, multidisciplinary and inter-sectoral research, monitoring, investigation, data recording and data sharing.
- ✓ **Invest in Specialist Training & Capacity:** Continue professional development for armed and security forces, customs, police, prosecutors and judges, and develop dedicated specialist investigators, prosecutors and judges to improve access to justice and deter criminality.
- ✓ **Harmonise Cross-Border Rules & Procedures:** Improve joint rules, regulations and procedures to facilitate cooperation among EU member states and candidate states.

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